

UDC 025.5:027.7(510+477)
DOI: 10.31866/2616-7654.7.2021.233273

**INFORMATION LITERACY
PROGRAMMES:
THE EXPERIENCE
OF RESEARCH LIBRARIES
IN HONG KONG
AND UKRAINE**

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The article is devoted to the analysis of information literacy programmes developed by libraries of higher education institutions in Hong Kong and Ukraine.

The application of such theoretical and empirical methods as an analysis of sources, the method of external observation over the foreign and Ukrainian experience of the information literacy programmes developing, as well as a prognostic method for summarising, allowed to reveal similarities and differences in the content and forms of information literacy programmes implemented at Hong Kong and Ukrainian universities.

Different stages of implementation of information literacy programmes by the Chinese University of Hong Kong (CUHK) Library during the last two decades are highlighted. The content of information literacy programmes provided by the libraries of 4 Ukrainian universities in general and the scientific library of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts (KNUCaA), in particular, is reviewed.

It has been found out such similar characteristics of information literacy programmes of libraries that were analysed as using of traditional forms (lectures, practical exercises, instructions, video lessons) to form the skills and abilities for the effective information search, analytical processing, organisation, evaluation, and use of this information. It has been found out that, unlike Hong Kong, the introduction of certified and online information literacy courses by Ukrainian universities libraries is isolated cases. There is also no experience in testing students' knowledge before studies of information literacy. Testing is usually done after completing the information literacy programmes, but these tests are not mandatory and only recommended.

The authors hope that the experience of the CUHK Library (Hong Kong) in the implementation of the "Immersion Programme", the UGCIL project, and InfoLit for U will be useful for the Ukrainian scientific library community, considering that libraries of higher education institutions in Ukraine have also started to develop similar programmes and modules. In particular, the interactive online guide "Music Documents in the KNUCaA Scientific Library" is an example of a modern approach to the formation of first-year students' information literacy, their acquaintance with the scientific library, its services, and resources, basic types of documents, an electronic search algorithm.

Keywords: higher education, university libraries, higher education libraries, information literacy, programmes, certified courses, tests.

INTRODUCTION

Formulation of the problem. Information literacy plays an important role in the development of the digital knowledge society by improving the quality of the scientific work of students and scientists. Academic libraries abroad use various information literacy programmes for university students, such as library orientations, library skills programmes, library research, information skills for senior/graduate students; special information skills programmes for database search and Internet search. The programmes are mainly focused on students acquiring information retrieval skills and their understanding of the ethical aspects of information usage.

Global informatisation of society, growth of information volumes, the rapid development of information technologies influence the evolution of concepts “information culture”, “information literacy”, “media information literacy”, and so on. These trends affect the research of the experience of implementing information literacy programmes in higher education libraries in foreign countries and Ukraine.

The issue of information literacy (information culture) is the subject of scientific interests of Ukrainian and foreign scientists: I. Bezzub, O. Fedorov, D. Gillmore, Yu. Horban, S. Hrypych, T. Hranchak, R. Kyuubi, S. Leungand, G. Tam, L. F. Li, L. F. H. Maand, L. Ko, M. Makarova, C. McNaught, S. Nosova, O. Osyukhina, O. Palekha, Yu. Palekha, F. Rogou, S. Sheibe, C. Storey and S. Leung, and others. It should be noted that the term “information culture” is more often used among Ukrainian scholars, while the publications of foreign researchers mostly use the term “information literacy”, “digital literacy”, “media literacy”. The research mainly deals with such aspects as understanding the concept of “information literacy” and its key principles (Bruce, 2000; Doyle, 1994; Jarson, 2010; Hranchak, 2018); recommendations for the creation of information literacy programmes in school and university libraries (Lau, 2006), the essence of information culture at three levels: the culture of the information society, the information culture of the individual and the organisation (Palekha et al., 2020); projects and measures for the formation of information literacy in the libraries of higher education institutions (Bychko & Matsei, 2013; Hrypych & Buravkova, 2019; Steshenko, 2018), including through gamification (Horban & Skachenko, 2019), the comparison of information literacy programmes in different universities (Li et al., 2007; Ma & Ko, 2016; McNaught et al., 2004; Moyo & Mavodza, 2016; Rasaki, 2009; Renditiso, 2011).

The research focus of Ukrainian scientists was the international experience of information literacy in general and in the context of libraries in particular. Thus, the following aspects were considered: cooperation of libraries and teachers of French universities on the formation of information literacy among students (Shapiro, 2016); interpretation (understanding) of the concept of media literacy depending on the mentality and traditions of the world (Yaroslavtseva, 2018). However, the issue of identifying the best practices of foreign experience in the implementation of information literacy programmes and comparing them with the activities of libraries of Ukrainian universities requires more research.

The purpose of the article is to analyse and compare the information literacy programmes of the Chinese University of Hong Kong Library and information literacy programmes of libraries of Ukrainian universities, identifying similarity and defining effective approaches for libraries' future practices.

Tasks:

- to review the information literacy programmes of the Chinese University of Hong Kong Library, including the consortium project on information literacy implemented in Hong Kong;
- to review the information literacy programmes of higher education libraries of Ukraine, including the information literacy programmes of the Scientific Library of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts;
- to identify common features of these information literacy programmes of Hong Kong and Ukraine and to define effective approaches for libraries' future practices.

RESEARCH METHODS AND MATERIALS

Theoretical and empirical methods were used to achieve the goals and objectives: analysis of sources, consideration of basic terms, the method of external observation over the foreign and Ukrainian libraries' experience in the formation of information literacy, theoretical and prognostic method for summarising and identifying of similar and different characteristics of information literacy programmes in the libraries of Hong Kong and Ukrainian universities.

MAIN RESEARCH MATERIAL

Information literacy (IL) is a necessary condition for creating new knowledge, developing personal and professional competencies, and lifelong learning. The IL development process has a long history in the national traditions in different regions of the world. IL programmes in the higher education sector are especially important. In the vast majority of cases, such programmes are developed and implemented in the libraries of educational institutions, based on the best world or national IL standards, guidelines, recommendations, and so on.

Successful programmes and projects to promote IL in the higher education sector include A New Curriculum for Information Literacy (ANCIL) in the UK; Welsh Information Literacy Project in Wales; SWIM (Streaming Web-based Information Modules) in Denmark; INFOLIT, which was simultaneously implemented in 5 universities in South Africa.

1. Information Literacy Programmes at the Chinese University of Hong Kong Library.

As a comprehensive research university, The Chinese University of Hong Kong (CUHK) consists of nine constituent Colleges and offers a wide-range of full-time and part-time programmes, which lead to bachelor's degrees, master's degrees, and doctorates. In 2020, the total student enrolment and teaching staff were 21,405 and 1,677 respectively (The Chinese University of Hong Kong, 2020). The mission of the CUHK Library as a leading research library is to partner in the "creation, access, dissemination and preservation of knowledge to inspire and support The Chinese University of Hong Kong in its research, learning, and teaching" (The Chinese University of Hong Kong Library, n. d.). This section highlights several milestones in the implementation of information literacy programmes by the CUHK Library in the past two decades. It is however not the purpose of this paper to offer a complete account of the information literacy education delivered by the Library.

At the beginning of the 21st Century, the CUHK Library adopted two typical strategies to embed information literacy into the university curriculum: 1) setting up

faculty liaison programmes to collaborate with the faculty members; 2) hosting library instruction and induction courses for the university community.

The purpose of setting up the faculty liaison programme was to enable the faculty members to “fully appreciate existing services, understand available and new resources, and assist in the Library’s strategic development to parallel advances in the curriculum” (McNaught et al., 2004). The faculty liaison librarians offered subject-specific library instruction courses to faculty staff and students, while reference librarians charged with student instructional programmes. The CUHK Library also developed a certificate programme on information literacy entitled *Information Literacy Certificate Courses*. Participants were required to attend five consecutive sessions on information literacy skills before they could be granted a certificate issued by the Library. At the same time, given that this certificate programme was not a graduation requirement of the University, participants’ attendance was not, however, mandatory. Apart from this face-to-face certificate programme on information literacy, an online web-based instruction programme entitled *Web-based ULS Information Literacy Tutorial* was also developed to enhance the information literacy of library users. This online tutorial included topics: (1) Common misconceptions about information searching; (2) Types of information sources; (3) Timeliness of information sources; (4) Formats of information sources; (5) When to use different categories of information sources; (6) How to locate various information sources; (7) How to evaluate information sources; (8) Citation styles; (9) Check your skills (URL in the reference list) (McNaught et al., 2004).

Recognising the importance of information literacy in the digital learning and working environment, the CUHK rolled out the mandatory *Student IT Proficiency Test* in the academic year 2006–2007. There were five sections in the Student IT Proficiency Test, namely (1) Basic operation of a computer, (2) Using computer application software, (3) Computer ethics and copyrights, (4) Information security, and (5) Information literacy, the newly added component. In the information literacy section, the University decided to adopt the *Web-based Information Literacy Tutorial* developed by the CUHK Library as the courseware of the Test. Based on the experience of the previous *Web-based ULS Information Literacy Tutorial*, the new *Web-based Information Literacy Tutorial* has been created according to the Information Literacy Competency Standards for Higher Education defined by the Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL) in the United States. This Tutorial contains seven modules: (1) Types of information sources and their characteristics; (2) Effective search strategies; (3) Use of the library catalogue; (4) Use of research databases; (5) Use of the Internet; (6) Evaluation of information sources; and (7) Citing information sources. The Tutorial was designed in such a way that there were a number of interactive activities such as games, drag and drop, text entry, and questions and answers to engage students in the learning process. It was a graduation requirement for all undergraduate students to pass the online IT Proficiency Test. As rightly pointed out by Li, Leung & Tam, “the integration of information literacy into a university’s competency-based mastery programme does not diminish the reference librarian’s teaching role but rather strengthens it” (Li et al., 2007).

ACRL Information Literacy Immersion Programme.

An important issue of implementation of information literacy programmes is the professional training of librarians, who could conduct training and teach others in

the future. *The Information Literacy Immersion Programme* (“*Immersion Programme*”) initiated by the ACRL was aimed at achieving this goal among the others.

The “*Immersion Programme*” was launched in 1999 and provides information literacy training and education for librarians in the areas of pedagogy and leadership (ACRL, n. d.). The Immersion Programme is usually delivered on several days and consists of intensive training and motivational activities on all aspects of information literacy. It was the first time for ACRL to deliver the programme in the Asia region in 2013. Hosted by Joint University Librarians Advisory Committee (JULAC), the Immersion Programme was held from 3rd to 7th June 2013 at the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology Library with sixty-six participants from seventeen institutions in the region, fifty-four participants from Hong Kong and twelve from China, Singapore, and Taiwan.

The *Immersion Programme in Hong Kong* consisted of two tracks, namely *Teacher Track* and *Programme Track*. The Teacher Track emphasised enhancing, refreshing, or extending their individual skills for teaching information literacy programmes. The learning outcomes of the *Teacher Track* were:

- design meaningful instructional activities that address different learning styles, recognising different student motivations, backgrounds, and experiences, to address student learning needs in a coherent and systematic fashion;
- adopt a constructivist approach to information literacy instruction to develop a theoretical perspective and foundation for selecting teaching approaches and learning activities;
- teach from a learner-centred perspective to engage students in the learning process;
- analyse and assess personal teaching methods, habits, and styles to expand the pedagogical repertoire and shape diverse learning situations;
- assess student learning to inform and improve practice;
- develop and articulate a personal perspective of information literacy to make its applications to professional and personal life effective and meaningful;
- capitalise on personal leadership characteristics/potential to commit acts of leadership and affect change in institutional/professional practice (HKUST Library, 2016).

The Teacher Track covered in the Hong Kong programme included the following sections: Authentic Teacher, Learning Theory, Learning Styles, Presentation Techniques, Connecting Outcomes & Content, Student-centered Learning, Active Learning, Teaching with Technology, Leadership for Instructional Change, etc. On the other hand, the Programme Track focused on developing, integrating, and managing information literacy programmes for institutions. The learning outcomes of the *Programme Track* were:

- build partnerships/relationships with individuals and groups on campus in order to elevate information literacy to a campus-wide enterprise;
- regularly scan the campus and higher education environment in order to use information literacy as a catalyst for the library’s participation in educational transformation;
- engage in ongoing reflective practice in order to create and sustain renewal and growth of information literacy program development and leadership;
- exercise leadership within the library and throughout the campus in order to influence library, curriculum, and instructional decision;

- identify and garner resources in order to build the capacity necessary to accomplish an information literacy mission;
- value risk-taking and looking for the second right answer in order to engage in the creative process;
- develop a culture of assessment and continuous learning in order to capitalise on strengths as well as opportunities for change (HKUST Library, 2016).

The Programme Track covered in the Hong Kong programme included Leadership, Persuading and Influencing, Meeting Programme Outcomes, Campus Cultures & Collaboration, Staff Development, etc. Also, there were three plenary sessions on two common topics, Information Literacy and Assessment, for the participants of both tracks.

Six instructional librarians from the CUHK Library attended the Immersion Programme in Hong Kong; one of them took part in the Programme Track and five others – in the Teacher Track. In addition to acquiring new concepts of applying active learning to information literacy programmes, they also had the opportunities to discuss common challenges in instructional activities for the university community with colleagues from not only Hong Kong but also other Asian countries. The topics that were discussed included insufficient class time, large class size, inflexible classroom setting, inactive student participation, and fast-moving technological environment (Ma & Ko, 2016).

University Grant Committee Teaching and Learning Project on Information Literacy.

JULAC was funded by the University Grants Committee (UGC) of Hong Kong for three years (2015–2018) to implement a cross-institutional project “*Improving information literacy in Hong Kong higher education through the development and implementation of joint interactive multimedia programmes*” related to teaching and learning of information literacy. The Project was aimed to enhance information literacy among students in UGC-funded institutions by developing and implementing shared interactive multimedia courseware. After this project, students were supposed to be able to uplift their capacity to use the information for learning and to improve self-awareness as information-literate students. There were altogether five sub-projects under this main theme: (a) Assess the information and educational needs of undergraduate students at the beginning of the project; (b) Conduct research readiness self-assessment exercises for undergraduate students at the beginning as well as closer to the completion of the project for comparison sake; (c) Build up IL capacity of the academic librarians in Hong Kong; (d) Develop a joint information literacy courseware; (e) Develop IL courses together with faculty members by using the Course Enhancement Funds (The Hong Kong Polytechnic University Pao Yue-kong Library, 2016).

Among other deliverables of the Project, *InfoLit for U*, a free open-access MOOC on IL using the edX platform, was launched in February 2018 as a 24×7, self-paced, non-credit-bearing MOOC for undergraduate students. *InfoLit for U* (Fig. 1) consists of two modules, namely the focal module and the disciplinary module. These two modules are designed to help students become analytical, wise, and creative information users for effective learning at the university and tackle professional challenges after graduation. In the focal module, “Not only search skills: What is InfoLit for U study & career?”, students will acquire the knowledge of using information for university-level inquiry works through five sections:

- Think & plan the “Info Needs” of your research;
- Don’t find answers: search for ideas to develop ideas;

- Not just filter: evaluate ideas to form new ideas;
- Never list them: connect ideas to create your idea;
- Stay hungry: join & learn from communities (The Chinese University of Hong Kong, 2017).

Figure 1. InfoLit for U.
URL: <https://cutt.ly/DzsvQM8>.

There are altogether eight discipline-related elective modules, namely Arts & Humanities, Business & Economics, Education, Engineering, Health Sciences, Law, Science and Social Sciences. These modules provide an inquiry-based context within which information-seeking tasks related to these disciplines are designed including:

- find discipline/task information;
- evaluate discipline/task information;
- create task outputs.

The student will be awarded an achievement certificate by this MOOC after completing the focal module plus at least one of the discipline-related modules with a 70 % or above the correct rate in the assessment questions test (The Chinese University of Hong Kong, 2017).

2. Practices of Higher Education Libraries in Ukraine.

Information literacy (information culture) activities are traditionally among the leading directions of Higher Education Libraries in Ukraine. Different traditional forms of work are related to such an activity: lectures/courses on information culture, information literacy schools, Information Days, Department's Days, Specialist Days, individual consultations, etc.

According to the results of the search for scientific publications on information literacy programmes implemented in the libraries of higher education institutions of Ukraine, this part of the article summarises and presents the experience of 4 university libraries.

During 2008–2012, in the *Khmelnysky National University Scientific Library*, IL training was conducted within the framework of the project “*From Information Culture to the Quality of Education*”. The objectives of the project were as follows: to increase the level of information culture of students and teachers of the university; to promote the library’s e-resources; to develop modern information services according to the needs of users. The main form of improving information culture was “individual counselling... by the process of reference and bibliographic services” (Bychko & Matsei, 2013, p. 492). During the studying, they used their library and remote e-resources, in particular a search in the database of the National Library of Ukraine named after V. I. Vernadsky. The project’s structure consisted of two parts: “Fundamentals of information culture and bibliography” lectures and practical classes for first-year students and “Scientific search for information. Sectoral bibliography” for undergraduates (Bychko & Matsei, 2013, p. 494).

The Rivne State University of Humanities Scientific Library uses various forms and methods for the IL formation among students and teachers: individual, group lectures, workshops, complex activities. For this purpose, the library produces a variety of information content: manuals, virtual exhibitions, multimedia presentations, etc. For instance, to enhance and visualise information about the structure, services of the library – during classes with freshmen shown a video “RSUH Scientific Library realises your right to information” (Hrypych & Buravkova, 2019, p. 37).

To support the research work of the university departments, teachers, and masters, the Information Center for the young researchers was organised in the library structure. As part of the cycle “Scientific Communications” the library holds information seminars and workshops: “Scientometric and bibliographic databases”; “International styles of design of scientific publications”, during which “methods, search schemes, determining the index of citations of printed publications of teachers are clearly demonstrated” (Hrypych & Buravkova, 2019, p. 36).

The COVID-19 pandemic led to libraries’ transition to remote work and the remote customer service organisation.

For example, *the Sumy State University Scientific Library* offers students an electronic resource “Fundamentals of Information Culture”, highlighting 4 components of information culture: media literacy, IT literacy, IL, digital identification (Sumy State University Library, 2019). General concepts and practical advice on academic integrity and IL are contained in the “Handbook on Academic Integrity” prepared by the library specialists (Hurianova et al., 2018).

Scientific Library of the O. M. Beketov National University of Urban Economy in Kharkiv has developed a distance course, “*Information resources of the KNUUE Scientific Library 2020*” for first-year students of all specialities on the Moodle platform. The course is taught during 1 semester; aims to form students’ set of skills and abilities for individual information activities (Kharkiv National Academy of Urban Economy, 2020, p. 21).

The Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts Scientific Library’ Programme “Information Literacy for Learning and Science”.

The purpose of the Programme is to develop users’ skills in information retrieval, evaluation, and responsible practical use.

Objectives of the information literacy programme:

- to form the students and young scientists’ basic IL skills and abilities;
- to acquaint with sources of information, search tools, search algorithm,

- to develop skills and abilities to evaluate information and its ethical use (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Goals of the KNUCaA Scientific Library Information Literacy Programme. Developed by the authors.

Activities for first-year students are aimed at mastering basic information literacy skills, organised jointly by librarians and subject teachers, and take place in two stages. During the 1-hour tour, students get acquainted with the library's physical space, the general rules of work, register as library users. Students attend lectures in the information and bibliographic department in the second stage. They get acquainted with the reference apparatus, reference, bibliographic fund, catalogues system, etc. During practical classes, algorithms of search of various types of sources in the electronic catalogue are studied, skills of an estimation of the materials that were found concerning the relevance of search, urgency, reliability, the authority of authors, and sources are checked.

After classes, students also acquire skills and abilities to formulate information requests. They perform an independent search in library catalogues, full-text databases; get the best of Internet resources and the library website; improve their ability to evaluate the found information and apply it correctly during training.

A creative event to form information literacy skills through games, which has gained popularity among first-year students, became the Information Games project, initiated and first conducted in the KNUCaA Scientific Library in 2018 (Skachenko, 2020).

The Scientific Library holds important activities to promote and support distance learning during COVID-19 quarantine. In December 2020, first-year students of the Faculty of Music were offered a "Musical documents in the fund of the KNUCaA Scientific Library" online library guide (KNUCaA Scientific Library, 2020, 1st December). The six parts of the virtual guide contain a description of the main kinds and types of musical documents available in the KNUCaA Scientific Library fund for scientific, educational,

creative work. The interactive guide also introduces to students the Scientific Library and its services, resources, the search algorithm in the electronic catalogue, and more.

Among the complex activities of the KNUCaA Scientific Library on the formation of information literacy are Master's Day, Postgraduate's Day, Department's Day, Information Week, which take place on the eve of 23rd April–World Book and Copyright Day.

The IL skills formation among *senior students, undergraduates, graduate students* aims to study the basics of research, compliance with copyright, the culture of academic integrity, etc.

During individual and group classes, young scientists:

1. Get acquainted with:

- library resources (fund composition, services);
- algorithm for writing abstracts;
- the structure of the annotation to the scientific article;
- basics of citation;
- styles of bibliographic references;
- structure of bibliographic record;
- rules for compiling bibliographic lists.

2. Study:

- strategies and tools for searching for information on the Internet, e-catalogues, and full-text databases;
- basics of working with texts (summarising, quoting, compiling, and annotation) and compliance with copyright.

After classes, young scientists can identify and interpret information correctly, skills of search, collection, and analysis of information, including preparing and compiling abstracts, annotations, selection of citations; registration of references, and observance of academic integrity norms, etc.

To form the skills and abilities to write scientific papers, the scientific and methodological department staff prepared methodological advice “Fundamentals of scientific research”. In particular, the research stages were revealed, the types and volumes of scientific articles, requirements to their structure and design were characterised.

The multimedia presentation “What a terrible beast is a scientific article, and how to stop being afraid of it” provides more examples, illustrations, life hacks, the discussion of the scientific research issue (KNUCaA Scientific Library, 2019, 26th December). The presentation contains sections of methodical advice concerning registration of lists of bibliographic references and the APA referencing style, Harvard referencing style; basics of academic integrity, and the ability to distinguish between plagiarism, self-plagiarism, fabrication, deception, etc.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of IL programmes implemented by the Chinese University of Hong Kong Library and the university scientific libraries in Ukraine revealed their similar and distinctive characteristics. Similar characteristics of information literacy programmes of libraries that were analysed include using traditional forms (lectures, practical exercises, instructions, video lessons) to form skills and abilities for the effective

information search, analytical processing, organisation, evaluation, and use of this information.

It has been found out that, unlike Hong Kong, the introduction of certified and online information literacy courses by Ukrainian universities libraries has isolated examples. There is also no experience in testing students' knowledge before studies of information literacy. Testing is usually done after completion of the information literacy programme, but these tests are not mandatory and only recommended.

In this regard, the experience of the CUHK Library (Hong Kong) in the implementation of the "Immersion Programme", the UGCIL project, and InfoLit for U will be useful for the Ukrainian scientific library community, considering that libraries of higher education institutions in Ukraine have also started to develop similar programmes and modules.

In particular, the interactive online guide "Music Documents in the KNUCaA Scientific Library" is an example of a modern approach to the formation of first-year students' information literacy, their acquaintance with the scientific library, its services and resources, basic types of documents, an electronic search algorithm. After library classes on information literacy, students are able to formulate information requests competently, do a search in catalogues and databases independently, process information analytically, evaluate and apply information critically, adhere to the norms of academic integrity.

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УДК 025.5:027.7(510+477)

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ПРОГРАМИ ІНФОРМАЦІЙНОЇ ГРАМОТНОСТІ: ДОСВІД АКАДЕМІЧНИХ БІБЛІОТЕК ГОНКОНГУ ТА УКРАЇНИ

Стаття присвячена аналізу програм інформаційної грамотності, розроблених бібліотеками закладів вищої освіти Гонконгу та України.

Застосування теоретичних та емпіричних методів: аналізу джерел, вивчення зарубіжного та українського досвіду розробки програм інформаційної грамотності, а також прогностичного методу для підведення підсумків, дозволило виявити подібні та відмінні риси у змісті та формах програм інформаційної грамотності, що реалізуються у бібліотеках університетів Гонконгу та України.

Висвітлено етапи впровадження програм інформаційної грамотності Бібліотекою Китайського університету Гонконгу (CUHK) за останні два десятиліття. Здійснено огляд змісту програм інформаційної грамотності у бібліотеках 4 українських університетів загалом та наукової бібліотеки Київського національного університету культури і мистецтв зокрема. Виявлено, що серед подібних характеристик програм інформаційної грамотності аналізованих бібліотек, є використання традиційних форм (лекції, практичні вправи, інструкції, відеоуроки) формування навичок і умінь ефективного пошуку інформаційних джерел, їхнього аналітичного опрацювання, упорядкування, оцінки, використання. З'ясовано, що на відміну від Гонконгу, впровадження сертифікованих та он-лайн курсів інформаційної грамотності в бібліотеках українських університетів має поодинокі приклади. Також відсутній досвід тестування знань студентів до початку навчання ІГ. Зазвичай тестування проводиться після завершення навчання за програмою ІГ, але ці тести є рекомендаційними, а не обов'язковими.

Автори сподіваються, що досвід бібліотеки CUHK (Гонконг) щодо реалізації "Програми занурення", міжвідомчого проекту UGC та InfoLit для U буде цікавим для української наукової бібліотечної спільноти, адже бібліотеки закладів вищої освіти України також починають розробляти подібні програми та модулі. Зокрема, інтерактивний онлайн-гід «Музичні документи у фонді Наукової бібліотеки КНУКіМ» є прикладом нового підходу до формування інформаційної грамотності студентів першокурсників, їхнього знайомства з науковою бібліотекою, її послугами та ресурсами, основними видами і типами документів, алгоритмом пошуку в електронному каталозі тощо.

Ключові слова: вища освіта, бібліотеки університетів, інформаційна грамотність, програми, сертифіковані курси, тести.

Стаття надійшла до редакції 03.03.2021 р.